

Synthesis of 3,4-Dihydro-5,6-Dimethoxyisocoumarin

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Manuscript received 16 September 1976, revised 16 May 1977, accepted 24 May 1977.

2-Nitro-*o*-homoveratric acid has been prepared by direct nitration of *o*-homoveratric acid. The nitro acid was successively reduced with lithium aluminium hydride and sodium dithionite to 2-amino-*o*-homoveratryl alcohol. On diazotisation, Sandmeyer reaction and hydrolysis it gave 3,4-dihydro-5,6-dimethoxyisocoumarin.

3,4 DIHYDRO-5, 6-dimethoxyisocoumarin has earlier been synthesised by the oxidation of 5,6-dimethoxyisochroman¹. The same compound has now been prepared by the procedure adopted in the synthesis of mellein methylether². For this purpose 2-nitro-*o*-homoveratric acid³ was obtained by direct nitration of *o*-homoveratric acid in 24% yield. The identity of nitro acid was established by comparison with an authentic sample prepared by the earlier route³.

In the synthesis of 3,4-dihydro-7,8-dimethoxyisocoumarin⁴, it has been shown that lithium aluminium hydride reduction of methyl 2-homoveratrate afforded a mixture of 2,3,2'3'-tetramethoxy-6,6'-dihydroxyethylazobenzene and 2-nitrohomoveratryl alcohol, which as such or separately when reduced with sodium dithionite, gave 5,6-dimethoxy-2-aminophenethyl alcohol.

The precipitate was filtered, washed free of acid. Crystallisation from methanol afforded a yellow solid which melted between 108-16°. Repeated fractional crystallisation from methanol gave yellow needles of (I) (1.5g), m.p. 179-80°, undepressed on admixture with an authentic sample prepared by a different route³. The mother liquor furnished a yellow crystalline solid (2g), mp. 158-60°.

*2-Amino-*o*-homoveratryl alcohol* (II): A solution of 2-nitro-*o*-homoveratric acid (1.5g) in dry tetrahydrofuran (25 ml) was added dropwise to a stirred suspension of lithium aluminium hydride (0.8g) in dry tetrahydrofuran (25 ml) cooled to 10° and left for 2 hr. at room temperature. Excess of lithium aluminium hydride and complex were decomposed by careful portionwise addition of ice-water followed by 2 *N*-H₂SO₄ (20 ml).

I

II

III

Accordingly, adopting the same procedure the nitro acid (I) was reduced successively with lithium aluminium hydride and sodium dithionite to yield 5,6-dimethoxy-2-aminophenethyl alcohol (II), isolated as its hydrochloride. Finally, diazotisation of (II), its conversion into nitrile which was not purified and subsequent hydrolysis, followed by acidification, gave 3,4-dihydro-5,6-dimethoxyisocoumarin(III).

Experimental

M. Ps. are uncorrected

*2-Nitro-*o*-homoveratric acid* (I) :-*o*-Homoveratric acid (5g) was added portion wise to nitric acid (25 ml., d 1.42) with constant stirring, the temperature during addition was not allowed to rise above 0°. After addition was complete, the reaction mixture was left at 10° for 1 hr. and then poured into a large volume of ice

water. The combined extract was dried over potassium carbonate and evaporated to a dark red gum which was dissolved in methanol (25 ml) and water (20 ml). Sodium dithionite (2g) was added in two lots, when the dark red colour discharged to straw yellow colour. The solution was refluxed on water bath for a few minutes. After distilling most of methanol, the solution was extracted with chloroform (3x25 ml), the chloroform solution was extracted with 50% hydrochloric acid (2x25 ml). The acid solution was chilled mixed with chloroform (25 ml), basified carefully with ammonia, chloroform layer was separated and the aqueous layer was further extracted with chloroform (2x25 ml). The combined extract was dried over sodium sulphate and the solvent distilled to give a red oil which turned dark due to rapid oxidation in air. It was taken up in dry ether (25 ml), chilled and dry hydrogen chloride bubbled through when the amine hydrochloride (0.28g) separated as dark green needles.

It was sublimed (bath temp. 150°/1 mm) as white needles, m.p. 188-90°, decomposes with previous darkening. (Found : C, 51.0 ; H, 6.2% ; C₁₀H₁₆O₃NCl Requires C, 51.3 ; H, 6.4%).

3,4-Dihydro-5,6-dimethoxyisocoumarin (III): The hydrochloride of 2-amino-*o*-homoveratryl alcohol (0.2g) in hydrochloric acid (0.2 ml ; d 1.16) and water (5 ml) was diazotised with sodium nitrite (0.08g) in water (0.6 ml) at 0°. After neutralisation with sodium carbonate, the diazonium solution was added to a solution of potassium cyanide (0.2g), nickel chloride (0.18g) and sodium carbonate (0.1g) in water (6 ml) at 18° with stirring. The mixture was allowed to stand for 1 hr. and then heated to 80° for half an hour. The solution was cooled extracted with ether (3x20 ml), the combined extract was dried over sodium sulphate and ether distilled to give a red gum. The gummy material was refluxed with aqueous potassium hydroxide (10 ml ; 10%) for 2 hr., cooled and acidified with hydrochloric acid. The solution was filtered and extracted with chloroform (2x25 ml), the extract dried over sodium sulphate and the solvent evaporated to give a gum which

solidified after a few hours. It was sublimed in vacuo (bath temp. 100-5°/1 mm) to yield a white residue. Recrystallisation from ethyl acetate-petroleum ether afforded colourless needles (0.10g), m.p. 72-73°, undepressed on admixture with an authentic sample prepared by a different route¹. IR in CHCl₃ : 5.88μ (conjugated δ lactone).

Acknowledgement

I wish to thank Prof. A. B. Lal, Head of the Post Graduate Department of Chemistry, Bhagalpur University for providing laboratory facilities.

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